

Black Panther, Google, and Racism

How late-night googling revealed an anti-white-male invention bias and suppression in Google's search results

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Best viewed at: <http://bit.ly/3uHjsph>

racism

Noun rac-ism | \ 'rā-,si-zəm also -,shi- \

Definition of racism¹

1: a belief that race is the primary determinant of human traits and capacities and that racial differences produce an inherent superiority of a particular race

2a: a doctrine or political program based on the assumption of racism and designed to execute its principles

b: a political or social system founded on racism

3: racial prejudice or discrimination

Recently I was enjoying Black Panther for the fourth time. It's a good movie², not worthy of Best Picture³, but certainly of Best Costume and Best Original Score. In it, I was admiring the Queen Mother's head-dress (bottom-right; credit: NYT). It appeared, to me, to be related to aboriginal cultures (upon which this head-dress is definitely based⁴) who record the Perattian Thunderbolts of the Gods⁵, with their 56 rays descending from 250-1000 km above in the ionosphere towards the Earth⁶. At the time, I was unable to confirm this. But, I noticed that the head-dress made use of 3D printing⁷. This somewhat intrigued me and I began reflecting on how interesting the tone of the movie is in terms of invention fantasy. Don't get me wrong, I've always preferred Black Panther to Batman (and Ironman), as a figure of conservative/independent male, isolationist martial artist, and genius⁸.

¹ <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/racism>

² 79% Audience score is very accurate, https://www.rottentomatoes.com/m/black_panther_2018

³ Avengers: Infinity War was a superior film. 91% audience score

https://www.rottentomatoes.com/m/avengers_infinity_war

⁴ <https://www.pinterest.com/pin/484066659942219854/>

⁵ <http://becomingborealis.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/01/PerattetalTPS2007-Z-pinchAuroraB-1.pdf>

⁶ <https://plasmauniverse.info/downloads-petros/Peratt&YaoAurora-PrehistoryPhys-Scr-T131.2008c.pdf>

⁷ <https://www.materialise.com/en/blog/a-crown-fit-for-a-queen-3d-printing-hits-big-screen-black-panther>

⁸ <https://www.dailywire.com/news/27274/black-panther-review-deeply-conservative-movie-paul-bois>

However, the degree of mental gymnastics that the film used to actively portray the fictional Wakanda - an invention of white men⁹ - and their tech as superior or primary to real white male inventions¹⁰, was a bit astounding. But it is, after all, a *fantasy* story. However, I also had the feeling that the writers wanted the audience to believe the movie was possible or even reality. Nothing could be further from the truth! It is anti-historical. I have already done previous research to confirm my suspicions that white males were extremely dominant in the world-changing top 140 inventions of all time (see figures)¹¹.

Top Inventions by Race/Ethnicity

Top Inventions by Gender (if known)

Top Inventions of Human History Comparison

Figures 2-4: White Males vs. Other groups, top 140 inventions¹² of known history.

⁹ Stan Lee, Jack Kirby; <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Black-Panther-comic-book-character>

¹⁰ Even small things, like repulsorlift drive for ships, were first imagined in science fiction writings of white men.

¹¹ <http://bit.ly/2uajfwx>

¹² http://www.edinformatics.com/inventions_inventors/ example sample list used; more included to increase samples for minorities as the top 100 lists are even *more* dominated by white males. Again see [11] for sample data.

However now I was curious, “Who created 3D printing?”¹³ and that led me, after my confirmed suspicion to ask, “How many African-American inventors are there?” I found two primary sources, wikipedia¹⁴ and “Interesting Engineering”¹⁵. The answer they provided was 140. But in reviewing the list of prominent inventors and scientists, etc.. I was dismayed to discover (and through line-by-line verification¹⁶) that only 58 of these were actually inventors (and the number of black female inventors of note and originality was not in the Wiki article but were in the other article). Of these, only half (29) were Original inventors, creating original products. This is not proof of a padded article, but it is a shockingly small number compared to 140 listed¹⁷. Many of these products were of incredible importance to society, but many were also novel inventions¹⁸.

By comparison the English Inventors wiki article had 572 unique lines of inventions, the overwhelming majority of which are culturally and technologically/scientifically significant. The Wiki article on inventors (worldwide), had 300 entries for the U.S. alone, and obviously some of those were African-American inventors. I did enjoy learning some of the very important inventions made by African Americans, such as CCTV, the fire safe, refrigerator truck, blood donor bags, etc..., but nowhere did I find any indication that African Americans were absolutely vital to the creation of the technologies on display in Black Panther¹⁹. There were lots of project leaders in useful technologies, and one inventor of the ISA serial bus²⁰ for motherboards, an important step, but not crucial in the sense that it would have crippled the world to momentarily not have that device.²¹

In an era where English history is being re-visioned to contain prominent black actors as kings and English figures²², and even Superman is being considered to be re-race cast²³, I find the trend to black-wash history a bit disturbing and probably itself a form of the ‘soft bigotry of low expectations’, by not holding people accountable to reality itself.

The issue is that when we applaud people for inventions they did not create first, it actually undermines the amazing contributions of those inventions which are of great significance. For example, Walter Hawkins basically invented plastics, Marie V.B. Brown invented CCTV when she and her husband created the home security monitoring system, and Alice Ball whose discoveries led to the cure of Leprosy (and for which she was denied credit for so long). These are just a few of the incredible inventions. Almost all of the inventions are STEM-related, but many of them are blue chip, as well. However, none of them except perhaps the invention of plastic, were particularly on display in “Black Panther.” Undoubtedly a hot comb was used, in a manner of speaking, for wardrobe. But it is not the gist of the film to imply that Wakanda is a hidden (conservative, isolationist) country of hair-obsessed people. African Americans do pride themselves in looking good²⁴ ²⁵, but all films have wardrobe and makeup departments.

But I digress. Back to invention. The question is, how prolific are the numbers?

¹³ Chuck Hull, <https://3dinsider.com/3d-printing-history/>

¹⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_African-American_inventors_and_scientists

¹⁵

<https://interestingengineering.com/black-inventors-the-complete-list-of-genius-black-american-african-american-inventors-scientists-and-engineers-with-their-revolutionary-inventions-that-changed-the-world-and-impacted-history-part-two>

¹⁶ <http://bit.ly/2HjVt9Z>

¹⁷ And all of them important, notable, and in almost every case, heroes!

¹⁸ 3 products which were related to hair, the Super Soaker, the golf tee, 2 inventors worked on beds, one of which was novel. In total 3/28 of the Original inventions were novel, as compared to 11/58 of the total number of inventors.

¹⁹ Save the foundation of plastics.

²⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Industry_Standard_Architecture#Past_and_current_use

²¹ http://blog.vdcresearch.com/embedded_hw/2010/09/the-isa-bus-how-long-can-it-last.html

²²

<https://www.quora.com/Is-the-inclusion-of-black-actors-in-the-movie-Mary-Queen-of-Scots-based-on-reality-or-is-it-historical-revision>

²³ Superman is a zionist invention of two American Jewish writers, which was accepted by Christians for its reflective themes.

²⁴ <https://www.npr.org/2012/12/31/167720258/why-black-men-tend-to-be-fashion-kings>

²⁵ <https://www.vogue.com/article/rosa-parks-civil-rights-angela-davis-coretta-scott-king-civil-rights-movement>

Table 1: Inventors Listed

No	81	57.86%
Yes	58	41.43%
Unclear ²⁶	1	0.71%
Total	140	
vs English Inventors	572	10.14%
Original vs English	29	5.07%

The answer is that the list is not as prolific as *I and others want it to be*. It is more robust than white people (on average) would suspect. Far less than race hustlers, the NAACP, and all-black colleges would have the media believe, and probably about on par, that they are far under-advertised and underappreciated. In American media, the tendency is to focus on political activists, sports heroes, politicians (ironically never Thurgood Marshall), and of course rebellious hip-hop artists. That is probably a bad idea. Recently the NBA announced plans to create 12 teams in Africa²⁷, which given the incredibly small chances of becoming a *successful* professional basketball player²⁸, its obvious unfocus on STEM, the average IQ in African nations^{29 30}, and the appalling rate of bankruptcy amongst top black athletes³¹, is likely one of the *last* things Africa needs.

Here is the part that is a bit more depressing. I suspected that there were a few *embellishments* (given the source), which would tend to obfuscate the facts. Out of 2 of the inventors, they were in fact aides or improvements to 2 inventions for white males, and a 3rd was in my estimation not the inventor at all (of the syringe). Fully 8 of the listed 58 were really white male inventions: the electrolytic capacitor, the pacemaker, the syringe, the microphone, probability theory, the vertical axis wind farm (or credit should go to Persians), brain tumor surgery, and HVAC.

Some of these are incredible, life-saving developments, and I can see the tendency and desire to co-opt the credit for these, which may be as far as claiming, or as little as saying they “co-developed”. Given the number of African-American women unlisted and forgotten, and the one instance where the common belief was that it was a white male when it was a black male inventor, it’s probably *almost* even.

But it is still wrong to do.

Inventors Amongst 140 Listed African American STEM Pioneers

Figure 5

²⁶ It is unclear that Isola Oluwabusuyi invented the “double sided guitar” and the author found no references, and the claim is in doubt.

²⁷ <https://www.cnn.com/2019/02/17/africa/nba-africa-basketball-league/index.html>

²⁸ 0.03% <https://www.norwichcsd.org/Downloads/ProSportsOdds.doc>

²⁹ ~70-75 <http://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/008124630603600101>

³⁰ <https://brainstats.com/average-iq-by-country.html>

³¹ 68% of the top 42 bankruptcies in sports history, 84.9% of the money. <http://bit.ly/2HrZF6v>

In the end the number of total listed inventors, just compared to say, English inventors of non-novel items (not toys and general common items, thousands of patents, etc...) is low. It's right about par for population considerations, in some ways... but bear in mind this is only English inventors listed on Wikipedia³², and that is by no means an exhaustive reference.

Figure 6: % of Originality and out of 58 samples, how many were white³³

Figure 7: vs English Inventors

The fact is, that there is a very good reason not to engage in “reverse” “cultural appropriation” (if such a term is even real). It feeds the narrative to white supremacist groups that they are “being replaced” - hence the chants, “you will not replace us” at rallies that are designed to use hate and nationalistic ideologies to whip up anti-POC fervor and fear.

By promoting fantasy and obfuscating the hard facts of history, the narrative is fueling the lies of not only the leftist extreme but the ‘alt-right’ extreme as well, who also engage in Identity Politics. It is well known that “Black Panther” was seen as a lamppost to signal the rise in a non-white male identity politique.³⁴ It should not be forgotten either that the “Black Panther Party”³⁵ was a black supremacists militant group³⁶, which advocated violence³⁷, and had many of its leaders were arrested for criminal behaviors³⁸. Today, the rise of Black Hebrew Israelite³⁹ supremacists⁴⁰ hate groups⁴¹ directly mirrors the anti-white and especially anti-white male agenda⁴² of the far left extreme elements of the national politique⁴³.

³² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_English_inventors_and_designers

³³ Some might call this “splitting hairs” but isn’t that precisely the tribalistic identity territorialism on display from Black History Month to the claims that George Washington Carver invented peanut butter? (Which he did not, the Mayans did)

³⁴ <https://www.them.us/story/dear-white-gay-men-black-panther-is-not-about-you>

³⁵ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Black_Panther_Party

³⁶ <https://www.trackingterrorism.org/group/black-panthers>

³⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Black_Panther_Party#Shoot-out_with_the_US_Organization

³⁸ <https://vault.fbi.gov/Black%20Panther%20Party%20>

³⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xg97LQQF354>

⁴⁰ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OhqB_wjO15M

⁴¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=q4lvBZngQ54>

⁴² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EBdk5hDadYE>

⁴³

<https://www.usatoday.com/story/opinion/nation-now/2018/10/28/white-male-bashing-trend-dangerous-saritha-prabhu-column/1778385002/>

Some would argue these groups don't have any power, and therefore cannot be racist or are marginal as a problem. However, racism is **not** predicated upon power (that is a social marxist/deconstructionist and/or postmodernist revision, and invalid from an egalitarian perspective, which is to say a perspective of Justice⁴⁴), nor are these groups any longer marginal since the instigation of the Covington Catholic “doxxing” situation⁴⁵ which was clearly a specific hatred of a child (minor) for his white face⁴⁶. The coverup of the original perpetrators being Black Hebrew Israelites⁴⁷ is part of a greater effort to obfuscate criminal culpability of African Americans in general⁴⁸, which is one of the media’s least favorite topics.⁴⁹ Secondly, the hoax of Jussie Smollett led to a call to attack anyone who questioned the obviously fake narrative⁵⁰ as outright white racists⁵¹, and this gaslighting in the media⁵² and bird-dogging⁵³ has again been an attempt to obscure the blame of Jussie⁵⁴ and pundits⁵⁵ and celebrities⁵⁶ who supported him specifically by instigating anti-white-male hatred.⁵⁷

What does any of this have to do with black inventors? Well, it turns out that the false narratives are driven by those with something to gain from the extremism, division and reaction. Not only the media, but google itself. I found an article that detailed google’s own search results, quite obviously hiding white male inventors⁵⁸, and decided to investigate on my own. Here’s what I found:

Table 2 - Search Terms in google, and google image slider bar results⁵⁹

"American inventors"	Black listed	33	56.90%	Vs. 58
	White listed	19	6.33%	Vs. 300 ⁶⁰
"American inventors -African"	Black listed	0	0	
	White listed	24	8.00%	
"African American inventors"	Black Listed	44	75.86%	31.43%
	White Listed	0	0	
"English inventors"	Black Listed	0	0	
	White Listed	54	9.44%	Vs. 572

The 31.43% number is out of total 140 possible return options, as Google primarily uses Wikipedia as a source.

⁴⁴ Rule of law, Civil rights for all, respect for the individual and possibly innocent, “innocent until proven guilty, etc...

⁴⁵ <https://www.thewrap.com/gq-writer-regrets-call-for-doxxing-covington-catholic-high-school-students/>

⁴⁶ https://www.reddit.com/r/The_Donald/comments/aii9r3/looking_like_nick_sandman_covington_catholic/

⁴⁷

<https://www.usatoday.com/story/news/nation/2019/01/22/black-hebrew-israelites-covington-catholic-video-hate-group-otter-info/2643519002/>

⁴⁸ <https://cei.org/blog/obama-administration-undermines-school-safety-priorities-schools-adopt-racial-quotas-student>

⁴⁹ <https://www.city-journal.org/html/decriminalization-delusion-14037.html>

⁵⁰ Bleach and nooses at 2am?

⁵¹ <https://theundefeated.com/features/why-do-so-many-white-people-deny-the-existence-of-white-privilege/>

⁵² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dxj6mywn1QQ>

⁵³ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_lYOfYqnEfs

⁵⁴ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=E4lrb1GBb_Y

⁵⁵ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZB_5qwDdZJY

⁵⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TV5EIBLY3Uc>

⁵⁷ <https://www.vanityfair.com/news/2019/02/why-the-right-wing-media-is-so-furious-about-the-jussie-smollett-affair>

⁵⁸ <http://www.unz.com/isteve/great-moments-in-google-american-inventors/>

⁵⁹ Note that the term “white inventors” does not get an image slider bar at all, while all the other searches do.

⁶⁰ Vs. total U.S. inventors listed https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_inventors

search "American Inventors" on Google, image result

Figure 8: Demonstration of obvious over-representation in search term results

Figure 9: screenshot results for "American inventors", by S. Sailer

[14 Black Inventors You Probably Didn't Know About - ThinkGrowth.org](https://thinkgrowth.org/14-black-inventors-you-probably-didnt-know-about-3c0702c...)

<https://thinkgrowth.org/14-black-inventors-you-probably-didnt-know-about-3c0702c...>
Feb 26, 2017 - 14 Black Inventors You Probably Didn't Know About. Dr. Shirley Jackson. Dr. Shirley Jackson is an American physicist who received her Ph.D. from the Massachusetts Institute of Technology in 1973. Lewis Latimer. Marie Van Brittan Brown. Otis Boykin. Lonnie G. Johnson. Charles Drew. Marian R. Croak. Lisa Gelobter.

[African American Inventors | Scholastic.com](https://teacher.scholastic.com/activities/bhistory/inventors/)

teacher.scholastic.com/activities/bhistory/inventors/
Famous African American Inventors: An Interactive Teaching Resource for Grades 4-8.

Figure 10: screenshot result for "Black inventors" all good results

white inventors

All Images Shopping News Videos More Settings Tools

About 36,800,000 results (0.82 seconds)

Images for white inventors

A seriously racist hit piece

'What have white people ever done for us?' - BBC News - BBC.com

<https://www.bbc.com/news/blogs-trending-36765111>

Jul 11, 2016 - In the tweet Mr McPrivilege called on 'caucasiaphobes' to pipe down and be grateful for all the wonderful inventions that he credited to white ...

You've visited this page 2 times. Last visit: 3/8/19

Try to live without white inventions for 1 hour.

People Try To Live Without Black Inventions For 72 Hours - YouTube

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=g0Z-IB7r-L4>

Mar 17, 2018 - "I know for sure this was invented by a black man. I don't know how I know that, but it makes me happy." Check out more awesome videos at ...

This is a response to the google algorithms someone has made

Google-White American Inventors - YouTube

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ue-cbbVZkuY>

Mar 29, 2017 - Google-White American Inventors. Saul Maryus. Loading... Unsubscribe from Saul Maryus? CancelUnsubscribe. Working.

This is just patently untrue. It is all about culture. White people like inventing new things

American Inventors Are Mostly White Due to Opportunity Gaps | Fortune

[fortune.com : Tech : science](https://fortune.com/tech/science/)

Dec 5, 2017 - White children are three times as likely to become patent-holders as black children and only 18% of inventors are women. Even then, many of ...

Figure 11: Screenshots results for “White inventors”; majority filled⁶¹ with irrelevant⁶² or even racist⁶³ results

⁶¹ ~43 cm² / 117 cm² ~37% African American results shown, compared to 57% for “American inventors”

⁶² Note there is also one apparently ‘scary’ or occult reference; and several duplicates. No slider provided.

⁶³ Definition 2a and 3

Google results based on search terms

Figure 12: Statistical Significance of difference in representation shown (ordinal) vs search terms

Google Preference for African American Inventors (58) vs. 300 American and 572 English Inventors on Wikipedia

Figure 13: Statistical Significance of difference in representation shown (%) vs search terms

Conclusions

There are no ambiguous interpretations of the data. It shows a clear bias for certain terms. It is unclear how that bias is created (via AI-related algorithm, selective programming, or did a team manually program the list presented?). But, like the racial bias against “white pride” in search and wiki results vs. “gay pride” or “black pride,” the result is clear: there is an unambiguous anti-white male bias regarding white male cultural history.

What is worrisome to me as a white male father of three white males, is not that our history will be lost. But rather that people will be very confused. It was white males who killed each other in droves in the civil war over slavery and state’s rights. It was white males who wrote the founding documents, the world’s greatest bill of rights ever made, created real civil rights reforms and the Constitutional Republic, innovated the world, voted for women’s suffrage, and have tried to end poverty and slavery worldwide. The narrative that white men are the *cause* of the world’s problems is factually, historically untrue. For example Disney put in its film “Pocahontas” that the white men of Jamestown not only fired the first shots but killed the natives first. This is factually inaccurate⁶⁴. In fact, the white English had to relocate to a better fort⁶⁵ due to violence upon them from enemy tribes⁶⁶ of their principal interested trading partners. They were killed first, and fired second. But the common mainstream narrative is exactly the opposite.

This is dangerous and foolish. By in large, white men on average want People of Color to succeed⁶⁷ (enough to create affirmative action systems to deal with widespread inequities⁶⁸), and admire them (from music⁶⁹ to sports to comedy⁷⁰) often even more than their own history⁷¹. The irony is most African-Americans have 25% European DNA in highly significant portions so white history *is* black history⁷². It also isn’t helping African or Native Americans anymore than telling someone they can fly off a housetop roof would. It is creating extremely unrealistic standards of perfection (and belief in persecution⁷³) that directly contradict statistical fact, criminal data, hiding the ugly truth about the issues of violence⁷⁴, home life⁷⁵, single parenthood⁷⁶, education⁷⁷, and crime^{78 79} from the group that is most targeted by its own members for violence and homicide: black males^{80 81}. Additionally, african-americans (and white women⁸²) need to remember the incredible struggle of white women suffragettes, abolitionists, and emancipationists, just as white people need to remember the inventions of the black women who tend to be forgotten.

⁶⁴ <https://www.shmoop.com/jamestown/timeline.html>

⁶⁵ <https://www.historyisfun.org/sites/jamestown-chronicles/timeline.html>

⁶⁶ Powhatan; “1597: Powhatan conquered the Kecoughtans, a large a prosperous tribe at the mouth of the James River.”

⁶⁷

<https://www.deseretnews.com/article/900023481/most-black-males-reach-the-middle-class-or-higher-heres-what-drives-them-to-success.html>

⁶⁸ <https://hbr.org/2018/02/why-arent-black-employees-getting-more-white-collar-jobs>

⁶⁹ <https://atlantablackstar.com/2014/11/06/really-listening/>

⁷⁰ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Pcrv_bfH0Xk

⁷¹ <https://knpr.org/desert-companion/2019-01/open-topic-black-history-month-white-people>

⁷² <https://www.sciencemag.org/news/2014/12/genetic-study-reveals-surprising-ancestry-many-americans>

⁷³ <http://www.pewsocialtrends.org/2016/06/27/on-views-of-race-and-inequality-blacks-and-whites-are-worlds-apart/>

⁷⁴ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/8066496>

⁷⁵ <https://www.verywellmind.com/domestic-violence-varies-by-ethnicity-62648>

⁷⁶ <https://www.politifact.com/truth-o-meter/statements/2013/jul/29/don-lemon/cnns-don-lemon-says-more-72-percent-african-american/>

⁷⁷ <https://www.census.gov/content/dam/Census/library/publications/2016/demo/p20-578.pdf>

⁷⁸ <https://www.hks.harvard.edu/sites/default/files/centers/wiener/programs/pcj/files/PoliceandPublicDiscourseBlackonBlackViolence.pdf>

⁷⁹ <https://www.usnews.com/news/articles/2016-09-29/race-and-homicide-in-america-by-the-numbers>

⁸⁰ <https://nypost.com/2017/09/26/all-that-kneeling-ignores-the-real-cause-of-soaring-black-homicides/>

⁸¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Race_and_crime_in_the_United_States

⁸² <https://qz.com/1150028/gloria-steinem-on-metoo-black-women-have-always-been-more-feminist-than-white-women/>

African Americans deserve to know the **full** truth about Africa⁸³, African history^{84 85}, slave⁸⁶ trade⁸⁷, American history, invention⁸⁸, and Wakanda. That includes knowing about black⁸⁹ (and native^{90 91 92}) slave owners, confederate fighters^{93 94}, and all the negatives and positives, as well as, yes: celebrating the *real* black history. Black history in America is American History and white history is black history. Therefore, yes, **white history is American history**. The two are intertwined. Google does the world and African-Americans an injustice by over-representing one group in order to mollycoddle them as if they are children incapable of hearing the truth. Google also does those of European, Slavic, and Jewish descent a disservice by suppressing the dominant facts about invention history.

It may be tempting for detractors to cite the author's race (proving their own racism), or gender (proving their own sexism), in order to declaim scientific fact, history, and statistics. This is the modern version of Newspeak revisionism. The reality is the dictionary definition is the widespread colloquial, legal, rational, egalitarian, humanistic, and **correct** definition of racism. Attempts to deny the facts presented reflect the biases (and low ethical standards⁹⁵) that currently exists in academia designed to create win-lose propositions for asserted social hierarchies which are assumed to be white, heterosexual, patriarchal, and *exclusive*⁹⁶ in their basic mode of existence, despite all the facts of success of prominent black male, female, and female in general, persons. These assertions typically ignore the successes of Asians and Latinos, as a rule, as they detract from the flawed hypothesis. But in postmodernism, fact is irrelevant as compared to the 'morally right'⁹⁷ narrative. Because of this, post-modern arguments against free speech, rationalism, biology, math, and historical facts are inherently losing positions in any debate, regardless of the speaker. The **facts are primary**, and the author's dispositions are secondary. To engage the issue in reverse is itself to engage in ad hominem, albeit in dialectic form. Ad hominem is inferior to ad ratio.

⁸³ <https://foreignpolicy.com/2016/08/09/there-are-no-successful-black-nations-africa-diginty-racism-pan-africanism/>

⁸⁴ <http://www.oxfordbibliographies.com/view/document/obo-9780199846733/obo-9780199846733-0100.xml>

⁸⁵ <http://www.gsdr.org/docs/open/cc88.pdf>

⁸⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Slavery_in_Africa

⁸⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Atlantic_slave_trade

⁸⁸ Most will be surprised to learn a white man invented basketball, and the dunk!

⁸⁹ <http://listverse.com/2017/06/06/top-10-black-slaveowners/>

⁹⁰ <http://slavedwellingproject.org/black-slave-owners/>

⁹¹

<https://notevenpast.org/black-slaves-indian-masters-slavery-emancipation-and-citizenship-in-the-native-american-south-by-barbara-krauthamer-2013/>

⁹² <https://www.aljazeera.com/indepth/opinion/native-americans-adopted-slavery-white-settlers-181225180750948.html>

⁹³ <https://www.battlefields.org/learn/articles/black-confederates>

⁹⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Military_history_of_African_Americans_in_the_American_Civil_War

⁹⁵ <https://psmag.com/education/a-philosophers-hoax-embarrassed-several-academic-journals-was-it-satire-or-fraud>

⁹⁶ There is no evidence of exclusivity. Instead there is evidence for forced diversity training, programs, and encouragement of segregation *from the Left*. <https://www.thecollegefix.com/black-students-demand-segregated-spaces-white-students/>

⁹⁷ <https://twitter.com/60minutes/status/1082068489597267968?lang=en>

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